

INJURIES OF THE THORACIC AND LUMBAR SPINE AND THEIR SURGICAL TREATMENT.

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The purpose of the study. Determination of the clinical efficacy of transpedicular fixation (TPF) in the treatment of injuries of the thoracic and lumbar spine. Material and methods. 87 patients with injuries of the thoracic and lumbar spine were operated on. 56 (64.3%) of them had spinal cord injury accompanied by neurological deficiency. In all patients, TPF systems were used to stabilize the damaged segment of the spine. Results. The differentiated use of various options for eliminating the compression of the dural sac when using TPF for the treatment of patients with spinal injuries allowed to obtain good treatment results in 63 (72.4%) patients, satisfactory - in 23 (26.4%), unsatisfactory - in 2 (2.2%). Conclusion. In case of traumatic spinal canal stenosis in the thoracic and lumbar sections, the choice of the method of decompression of the dural sac should be planned individually for each patient, taking into account the period from the moment of injury, the severity and dynamics of neurological disorders, localization of spinal column damage.

Keywords: spine, trauma, stenosis, decompression, transpedicular fixation.

Spinal injuries and their surgical treatment are an urgent problem of modern vertebratology [1, 9, 12, 13,]. The transitional parts of the spine are most often damaged. The thoracolumbar transitional region accounts for about 58.4% of injuries, while in 30-70% of cases there is compression or damage to the spinal cord [2, 3, 8, 9, 14].

Along with early decompression of the spinal cord, the basic principles of surgical treatment of these injuries are full-fledged correction of traumatic deformation and strong stabilization of the damaged spine with the restoration of its support capacity for early activation of the affected [1-7, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14]. Of the modern methods of correction and stabilization of the spine, transpedicular fixation (TPF) provides the greatest opportunities for solving the main problems of damage treatment.

The aim of the study was to determine the clinical efficacy of decompression of the dural sac, reposition and stabilization of the spine when using TPF for the treatment of thoracic and lumbar injuries

Material and methods

We observed 87 adult patients with injuries of the thoracic and lumbar spine and traumatic stenosis of the spinal canal. Among them 66 men and 21 women from 17 to 68 years old. Traumatic spinal canal stenosis in all patients was measured according to CT or MRI data, stenosis ranged from 25 to 100% of the sagittal size of the spinal canal.

PDS injuries in patients were classified using the Universal Classification of Spinal Injuries [20]. 11 (12.4%) patients had A1 type fractures, 6 (3.5%) — A2, 21 (28.8%) — A3; 17 (15.9%) — B1, 15 (14.7%) — B2, 5 (2.9%) — B3; 7 (10.6%) — C1, 4 (4.7%) — C2, 1 (6.5%) — C3.

Damage to one PDS was recorded in 63 (72.4%) cases, two - in 24 (20.6%).

76 (68.2%) patients had spinal cord injury (PSMT) accompanied by neurological deficiency of varying severity, the remaining 11 (31.8%) had isolated spinal injuries not accompanied by vertebrogenic neurological disorders. In 74 (80.2%) patients, PSMT was localized at the level of Th10—L2 b, in 13 (19.8%) - L2—L3.

44 (38.0%) patients had lower paraplegia with full anesthesia from the level of injury and lack of sensitivity in segments C4—C5 (group A on the Asia/ISCSCI scale); 15 (16.4%) had lower paraplegia with preservation of sensitivity elements in segments C4-C5 (group B); 11 (31.0%) - neurological disorders in the form of lower paraparesis

(group C). 17 (14.6%) patients had a limited neurological deficit in the form of mild lower paraparesis, radicular syndromes at the level of damage (group D).

Neurological disorders in 9 (7.8%) patients tended to regress in the first days after the injury (in the acute and early periods of PSMT); in 73 (87.9%), the neurological status remained without clinically significant dynamics until the moment of surgery; in 5 (4.3%), signs of aggravation of neurological deficit were noted in the preoperative period.

54 (31.8%) patients with isolated injuries of the thoracic and lumbar spine, not accompanied by neurological deficiency, had spinal canal stenosis.

Patients with PSMT were hospitalized in the clinic within a few hours to 3 months from the moment of injury. 68 (58.6%) patients were operated on in the acute period of PSMT, 27 (31.9%) in the early period, and 2 (9.5%) in the intermediate period.

The average value of traumatic spinal canal stenosis in 46 patients with PSMT was 55.6%; in 31 patients with isolated uncomplicated injuries - 42.7%. Local kyphosis in injured PDS averaged 14.8° according to Cobb in patients with PSMT and 10.8° in patients with isolated spinal injuries. In patients with neurological deficiency, the vertical size of the ventral section of the injured segments was reduced to an average of 63.6%. In patients with isolated spinal injury, the decrease in the vertical size of the osteoligamental column reached 67.2%.

Of 67 patients with neurological deficiency, 23 (25.9%) had a single large fragment of the vertebral body with reversion ($\geq 15^\circ$ or more), and 12 (10.4%) had a single large fragment without reversion. Spinal canal stenosis of this type averaged 51.8% of its sagittal size. Traumatic stenosis with two free fragments of the vertebral body with reversion (and $\geq 15^\circ$ or more) occurred in 14 (12.1%) patients, without reversion - in 15 (12.8%). Stenosis of this type averaged 52.2% of its sagittal size. Spinal canal stenosis with several small fragments of the body or fragments of the roots of the arches and the broken arches themselves in the group of patients with neurological deficiency occurred in 19 (16.4%) cases and averaged 55.9%.

Dislocations (fractures) of the vertebrae were the cause of traumatic stenosis in 26 (22.4%) cases; the dislocation of the injured PDS averaged 34.9%, traumatic stenosis - 66.3% of its sagittal size.

In the group of patients without neurological deficit, in 15 (35.2%) cases, the cause of traumatic spinal canal stenosis was a single large fragment with reversion (15° or more), in 17 (31.5%) — a single large fragment without reversion. Stenosis of this type in patients with isolated spinal injuries averaged 41.4% of its sagittal size. Spinal canal stenosis with two free fragments with reversion was recorded in 8 (14.8%) cases, without reversion — in 7 (12.9%). Its average value is 45.3%. Traumatic stenosis with several small fragments, as well as fragments of the roots of the arches and the broken arches themselves in the group of patients without neurological deficiency occurred in 2 (3.7%) cases and averaged 66.5%. Dislocation (fracture) of the vertebra was the cause of stenosis in 1 (1.9%) case and amounted to 29.3%.

All patients underwent surgical treatment, including decompression of neurovascular formations of the spinal canal at the level of injured PDS, correction of anatomical relationships and reliable stabilization of the spine. In all cases, surgical correction and stabilization of the spine was performed using TPF of injured PDS. The spinal system "CHM" was used. TPF was used during one PDS in 4 (2.4%) cases, two — in 137 (80.6%), three — in 18 (10.5%), four — in 7 (4.1%), five — in 4 (2.4%). Four—screw spinal systems were used in 144 cases, and six-screw systems were used in 26 cases.

The choice of the method of performing decompression of the dural sac was determined individually for each patient. Whenever possible, preference was given to the least traumatic decompression options based on indirect repositioning reconstruction of the spinal canal. The preoperative planning took into account the depth and dynamics of neurological deficit, the period from the moment of injury, the spondylometric characteristics of traumatic deformation, the magnitude and type of spinal canal stenosis, the level of spinal injury. In each case, the possibility of

performing indirect repositional decompression due to the ligamentotaxis effect was predicted. In the presence of traumatic spinal canal stenosis and signs of regression of neurological disorders, spinal angiography (3 patients) and/or CT myelography in two projections (5 patients) were performed at the stage of preoperative planning to clarify the indications for various variants of decompression of the dural sac.

Laminectomy during TPF was performed in 52 patients. Open decompression of the dural sac from the posterior access was performed in 20 patients. Meningomyelodivulsiolysis was performed in 16 (9.4%) patients with severe neurological deficiency. After laminectomy, with persistent gross anterior compression of the dural sac, anterior open decompression was performed in 13 (7.7%) patients due to subtotal corpectomy during staged intervention on the ventral spine. 76 (44.7%) patients were operated on in the first three days after the injury; 11 (30.6%) after 4-14 days.). In 45 (47.1%) patients, decompression of the dural sac was performed without opening the spinal canal and achieved it during TPF due to the effect of ligamentotaxis. Among these patients, 29 (28.8%) - with isolated uncomplicated spinal injuries, 16 (18.2%) — with PSMT. In 39 (22.9%) patients with comminuted fractures of the vertebral bodies, a method of spinal canal reconstruction in comminuted fractures was used to eliminate spinal canal stenosis [11], the use of which provides selective maximum reponant effect on the elements of the middle osteoligmental column.

Results

Analyzing the clinical effectiveness of technical variants of TPF for injuries accompanied by traumatic spinal canal stenosis, we evaluated the possibilities of reposition of injured PDS and decompression of the dural sac with various variants of displacement, taking into account the time elapsed since the injury, regression of post-traumatic neurological deficit, as well as the stability of fixation of injured PDS during the consolidation of the vertebra or the formation of the intertidal bone the block after performing the corporodesis. The repositional capabilities of TPF in these types of injuries were characterized by indicators of correction of the main components of

traumatic deformation - spinal canal stenosis, local kyphosis at the level of spinal injury, transverse dislocations in injured PDS with subluxations and dislocations, deficiency of the vertical size of the ventral osteoligmental column. In patients with PSMT, the regression of neurological deficit, systematized according to the ASIA/ISCSCI scale, was characterized by the degree of restoration of the main functions of the spinal cord in the intermediate and late periods of PSMT, the stability of TPF — the frequency of cases and the amount of partial loss of correction in the postoperative period.

In the group of patients with posttraumatic neurological deficit, 9 patients tended to positive dynamics of neurological status before the start of surgical treatment. After the operation, positive dynamics up to the first stage on the ASIA/ISCSCI scale was achieved in 5 people, regression up to the second stage was noted in 3, and complete regression of neurological symptoms was noted in 1.

In a group of 5 patients with a tendency to negative dynamics of neurological status before the start of treatment, there was no regression in 2 people after surgery, positive dynamics up to the I st. was achieved in 2, improvement up to the II st. - in 1.

In the group of patients who had no changes in neurological symptoms before the operation, after the operation, positive dynamics up to the I st. was achieved in 30 cases, regression up to the II st. — in 26, up to the III st. — in 4. 35 patients had no changes in neurological status, mainly patients with severe neurological disorders (30 people — group A on the ASIA/ISCSCI scale, 2 — group B, 3 — group C).

After surgery, local kyphosis in injured PDS averaged 7.6° according to Cobb in patients with PSMT; the correction value averaged 7.2° . In patients with isolated spinal injuries, local kyphosis after surgery is 6.5° ; the correction value is 4.3° on average. After performing corporodesis, the loss of correction of local kyphosis in patients with neurological deficiency was 6.5° , without neurological deficiency — 2.9° .

The assessment of the immediate results of the treatment of unstable injuries of the thoracic and lumbar spine was carried out 2 months after the final surgical stage. Long-term results of treatment were studied a year after its completion.

The immediate results of treatment were followed in all operated patients: good results were obtained in 65 (78.8%), satisfactory — in 9 (19.4%), unsatisfactory — in 3 (1.8%). Unsatisfactory results of treatment are associated in two cases with the destabilization of the metal structure, which required in one case the rewiring of the metal structure, in the other — the extension of fixation higher by another level. In one case, after surgery, there was a persistent (deterioration from level C to A on the ASIA/ISCI scale) increase in neurological symptoms.

No significant loss of correction was observed in 26 patients in the long term (a year or more), in 4 patients due to the destabilization of the metal structure (fracture of screws, loosening of nuts) before the completion of the formation of the interbody bone block in the injured PDS, the average loss of correction was 16.2%; two of these patients underwent the re-installation of the TPF system.

Long—term results of treatment a year after surgical interventions were observed in 92 (54.1%) patients: good — in 73 (79.3%), satisfactory — in 16 (17.4%), unsatisfactory - in 3 (3.3%). In 1 patient, a fracture of one of the screws of the metal structure, the eruption of an adjacent screw with a developed coarse kyphotic deformation was revealed; in another 1, the untwisting of the fastening nuts of the polyaxial metal structure, which led to kyphotic deformation. In the first case, corporodesis was not performed at the second stage due to the patient's refusal, in the second case, corporodesis was performed at a late date (5-6 months). In both patients, the metal structure was reinstalled in the first 4-7 days.

Discussion

The obtained results showed that TPF allows to restore anatomical relationships in injured PDS, including reconstruction of the spinal canal, and to stabilize all supporting osteoligamental columns.

With dislocations or fractures, provoking gross deformation and stenosis of the spinal canal, but not accompanied by destruction of the back of the vertebral bodies and arches, reformation, as a rule, does not cause difficulties.

Analysis of the results showed that not every case of critical traumatic spinal canal stenosis with injuries to the thoracic or lumbar spine requires open decompression of the dural sac by corporectomy or laminectomy. In such cases, against the background of the absence of a neurological deficit or in the presence of a clear positive dynamics of the vertebral neurological status when using TPF, indirect decompression of the dural sac due to the effect of ligamentotaxis and reformation of the spinal canal by the repositional tools of the spinal system may be sufficient.

Conclusions

1. In case of traumatic spinal canal stenosis in the thoracic and lumbar sections, the choice of the method of decompression of the dural sac, taking into account the spondylometric characteristics of injuries in injured PDS, the period from the moment of injury, the severity and dynamics of neurological disorders, localization of spinal column damage.

2. For effective reconstruction of the spinal canal, it is necessary to use spinal systems that provide multidirectional force repositional effects on the implanted screws during surgery.

3. The decompression option based on the repositional reconstruction of the spinal canal is more preferable, since it provides minimal trauma of the operation, does not provoke the development of a rough scar-adhesive process in the spinal canal.

4. In case of untreated spinal canal stenoses in conditions of reliable stabilization of injured PDS, in the absence of neurological manifestations or with their complete regression, perform open reconstruction of the spinal canal.

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